

Work plan routine

- Filename and folder structure – be consistent and create README files if necessary
 - Filename recommendation: case study number_filename_YYYYMMDD
 - Folder structure: WP and case study number
- DDOMP team meeting
 - We will schedule a DDOMP team meeting every three months to check the work plan routine is updated regularly.
- Software, dataset, and code
 - Update the software and dataset log at least every three months, and the data managers will update it.
 - Ensure that updates of code (e.g., python code) are uploaded to GitHub after larger changes.
 - Use version control to keep track
 - Include a [Citation.CFF](#) and a [CodeMeta](#) file for documentation of your software
 - Deposit your data—ensure you follow the guidance from your selected repository and include metadata, README (if any), license chosen, and DOI.
- Team and stakeholder contact information
 - The List of partners will be updated whenever a change is needed (e.g., new team members joining, changing affiliation, or contact information); data managers are in charge of updating their individual teams' contact information.
 - The List of stakeholders will be updated whenever a change is needed (e.g., new stakeholder joining, changing contact person, or contact information); data managers are in charge of updating their individual affiliated stakeholder information.
- Backup
 - Ensure that a data lead manager backs up each institution's OneDrive at least every three months.
 - Ensure we have a local backup such as on local laptops.
 - In case of sensitive data, backups have to be stored with the same safety and security standards.
- Digital objects
 - The recommended preservation schedule could include the following points:
 - Project milestones such as a yearly report
 - Before and after significant decisions
 - Publicly disseminate research results such as oral presentations, posters, workshops, etc.
 - Research publication
 - Completion of the project
- Digital presence
 - Include your ORCID on all your works
 - Keep your (ORCID) profile up to date (every three months).
- Acknowledgement and citation
- Ensure that the routine for author acknowledgment is fulfilled before publication/upload to Zenodo.

Circularity3 DDOMP work plan routine
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11092807>

Commented [Au1]: [NOTE: weekly in case of PARSEC]

Commented [Au2]: [NOTE: PARSEC did it every week for non-peer-review and monthly for planned peer-reviewed publications]

Circularity³: DDOMP work plan routine

Circularity³

- Data citation – ensure proper credit is given for the data you used.